

Co-Evaluation of Climate Services. An analysis of the CLARA experience

E. Delpiazzi, F. Bosello

CMCC@Ca'Foscari, Ca' Foscari University of Venice, European Institute on Economics and the Environment (EIEE)

Application of the value of information theory

Co-Evaluation of Climate Services. An analysis of the CLARA experience

E. Delpiazzo, F. Bosello

CMCC@Ca'Foscari, Ca' Foscari University of Venice, European Institute on Economics and the Environment (EIEE)

